

Higher learning institutions, walk the talk. Assessing the health of the environment!

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Abstract

This paper is about an environmental health assessment of an academic institute. The primary purpose was to show how such an assessment could be done methodologically. Participation was vital in carrying out the assessment; few members of the Institute met to discuss the environmental health problems, their causes, effects, and possible mitigation measures with the help of problem and objective trees. The scorecard technique was used to rank the problems that affect human health, the quality of life of the people, and the causes of ecological problems. Air quality degradation scored higher. The key recommendation from the study is that higher learning institutions should start practicing what they teach regarding environmental health.

Keywords: Environmental health assessment, environmental problems, problem tree

1.0 Introductory background

The paper is about an environmental health assessment. Environmental health is a field of expertise that involves multidisciplinary actions to improve, regulate, and govern the environment's physical, chemical, biological, social, and psycho-social factors to reduce adverse health impacts (Moreno, nd; Cairncross & Kolsky, nd). Its assessment is about troubleshooting the health problems, their causes and effects, and measures for mitigation (Environmental Law Institute, 2000; CDCP, 2008). People's health depends on the environment in which they live (CDCP, 2008; Bahauddin & Uddin, 2012). People may wish to live in a healthy environment and reduce the hazards of an unhealthy environment; they may, as well, make different choices because issues concerning community health are political, and hence demand the participation of

a wide range of actors (Environmental Law Institute, 2000; CDCP, 2008).

The paper aims at providing an understanding of how such an assessment can be done in a higher learning institution. Such an understanding is crucial for higher learning institutions for several reasons. One, such institutions have many experts who, in one way or the other, can be helpful in the daily practices of keeping the environment healthy. Two, it is in such institutions that teaching is done, and hence potential spaces for a multiplier effect in dealing with the environment's health through the transmission of environmental health assessment protocols to students. Last but not least, due to ongoing research activities in such institutions, creative ways of dealing with the health of the environment can be invented.

The paper continues with the methodological underpinnings that present the issue of participation and the description of the Institute in which the assessment was done. In another section, there is a presentation of the environmental health problems, followed by the suggested solutions. The paper winds up with the prognosis, describing the environmental health vision of the Institute.

2.0 Methodological underpinnings

A participatory methodology from a guidebook for local health officials by the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention was adopted (CDCP, 2008). Twenty-one members from IRDP were selected with the help of Heads of Department to form a Project Team. The team members held specific positions at the Institute, committed themselves to invest time, and were concerned with the environment, well-being, and quality of life.

The primary method for data collection was group discussions and observations. The team met and discussed for four hours consecutively and brainstormed on the environmental problems, their causes, effects, and possible mitigation measures. After the brainstorming, the team categorized the problems in human health, ecological, and quality of life problems. The team came up with the core problem-using the scorecard ranking technique.

Two big trees were drawn on the flip charts: one for the problems and another for the solutions; participants wrote problems and solutions on sticky cards, then placed them on the drawn tree (See, Figure 1). The problem tree helps to bring to light cause and effect relationships leading to the primary problem, which otherwise would not feature in

the planned intervention (Dillon, nd; Narayanasamy, 2009). Elaborating on this, Evaluation Toolbox (2010) notes,

Conducting a problem tree/solution tree analysis provides a means to review the current understanding of the causes of a specific problem and how it can be overcome. A problem tree will likely reveal multiple branches (cause & effect relationships) leading to the core problem. This is valuable as it identifies factors that the planned intervention may not address. For example, existing regulations may be a factor in the problem, but the planned intervention may not impact this.

This may fail to achieve project objectives. It could be that impacting upon regulation is not achievable and thus out of scope for the project. If this is the case, then the evaluators need to account for this when the intervention is evaluated (Evaluation Toolbox, 2010: 2).

After identifying the environmental health problems facing IRDP, reviewing all existing sources of information on environmental problems, analyzing the information, the problem statements were prepared for the team to create a future environmental health vision, with the significant concern about how IRDP should look like in not less than a generation to come in the field of the natural environment, land use, infrastructure and services, economic growth, community health, and quality of life.

The study was conducted at the Institute of Rural Development Planning (IRDP), which is one of the higher learning institutions in Dodoma. This paper began as an extensive assignment I undertook when writing my Ph.D. thesis. After submission, it was reviewed and worked upon for publication. The Institute of Rural Development Planning (IRDP), where the assessment was done, is a higher learning institution in Mbwanga Ward in Dodoma, Tanzania. It is located 8 km from Dodoma City Centre along the Great North Road from Cape Town in South Africa to Cairo in Egypt. The Institute offers training, research, and consultancy services in rural development planning and management. The Institute is in a 40,000 square meters fenced plot with 18 buildings.

The Eastern side of the Institute passes the Great North Road, which is under construction to upgrade to a tarmac road. According to Bradford (2015), construction activity is the primary source of environmental pollution in noise and air pollution. Noise pollution comes from heavy construction machines and trucks' movement. Air

pollution comes from dust from construction works and vehicles passing at the loose earth road used temporarily for diversion during road construction. Other parts of the Institute are not paved, and no grass covers to reduce dust from the wind. The Campus has 5,000 students and 235 staff, of which 282 students are accommodated on Campus in a three-floor building, with each floor having eight toilet facilities, eight bathrooms, and eight washing bowls. These shared toileting facilities for 94 students, though within the national standards for boarding facilities, cause challenges during rush hours.

In most cases, these facilities are used by many students without any interval to allow cleaning and disinfection. This situation contributes to students' contamination and spread of skin and Urinary Tract Infections (UTI). The toilets are connected to 5 septic tanks and five soak way pits emptied by truck.

A dispensary within the Institute premises offers medical services to the IRDP community and the surrounding people. Typical diseases treated at this dispensary are coughing, skin diseases, UTI, and diarrhea. The Institute has 180 meters deep well to supplement water supply services from Dodoma Urban Water Supply Authority (DUWASA).

This well is located 4 meters from the Institutes' standby diesel engine electric generator and 10 meters away from a soak way pit that serves three small restaurants. No pumped water test was done more than five years ago since its inception. Regular water test for common water problems like bacteria, pH, nitrate, and other dissolved compounds such as oils spill from the nearby standby diesel-powered electric generator is essential for water quality.

The Campus has three canteens that offer meal services to students and staff. The canteens use fuelwood charcoal for cooking, with an average of one to three bags of 80 to 90 Kg each a day. These canteens use cooking stoves made of recycled heavy truck metal wheels (See Plate 1). Also, the canteens use weak acid for floor tiles cleaning, which could cause underground water source contamination. On Campus, there is a burnt container (See Plate 2); around this container are burnt trees and loose soil, one of the dusty sources.

There are also three old abandoned vehicles (2 land cruisers and one truck) turned into a dumping site for broken beds and furniture (See Plate 3). Medical wastes are collected using color-coded dustbins, each color indicating a type of waste and management practices required for disposing of waste; red dustbins and safety boxes are for infectious medical waste; yellow dustbins are the less infectious medical waste

(See Plate 4); black dustbins are for non-infectious medical waste. All dustbins should be fixed with plastic bags of the same color. The Institute has also dumping pits for solid wastes disposal and an incinerator within the compound (See Plate 5 & 6).

3.0 Environmental health problems and solutions

The identified environmental health problems were categorized in terms of human health, ecological, and quality of life problems, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Environmental Health Problems

Human health	Ecological	Quality of life
Cold and flu	Wind	Stress
Coughing	Dust	Depression
Fungus	High temperature	Unhappiness
Skin disease	Pollen	
Asthma	Storm water stagnation	
Urinary Track Infection (UTI)		

Source: Field data, 20th August 2016

The team was encouraged to develop the core problem-using scorecard ranking technique. After subjecting the identified problems to the scorecard technique of ranking, deteriorating air quality scored high (8 out of 10). The team was in agreement with the scorecard results. It was argued that the deteriorating air quality causes stress and depression of the people; this leads to human health problems and ecological problems, a finding supported in the studies made by the Environmental Law Institute (2000) and by Briggs (2016).

For instance, cold, flu, cough, and asthma were related to air quality; and ecological problems, such as wind, dust, weather changes, and pollen, have something to do with air quality. Similarly, air pollution is the leading environmental health problem, as the WHO (2014:1) noted:

in 2012 around 7 million people died - one in eight of total global deaths - due to air pollution exposure. This finding more than doubles previous estimates and confirms that air pollution is now the world's most significant single environmental health risk. Reducing air pollution could save millions of lives.

A problem and solution tree were developed from the identified core problem, as shown in Figure 1.

From the identified environmental problems facing IRDP to one that seemed core, the solution to the problem was sought. It was agreed upon that improved air quality was necessary to deal with the deteriorating air quality. Around this solution, a solution tree was constructed. The details of the solution tree are found in the following Figure 2.

Figure 2: Solution Tree

Source: Compiled from field data, 23rd August 2016

4.0 Discussion of the findings

Deteriorating air quality at IRDP is a general challenge at IRDP and in most institutions that offer training, research, and consultancy. A Swahili says that "penye miti, hapana wajenzi" (where there are trees, there are no builders). Such institutions have experts who could conduct environmental health assessments. However, this is hardly done. Part of the reason is the lack of backup institutions to push the exercise. At IRDP, the environmental health assessment is taught but not practiced by the same Institute. This could be a severe problem for the graduates who are potential future environmental health managers and politicians: environmental health managers and politicians who never walk the talk regarding environmental health.

The lack of plastic bags to avoid contaminating the container, as shown in Plate 4, is caused by the shortage of funds, which is an economic problem, as Moreno, nd; Cairncross & Kolsky, (nd) points out. The location of the incinerator at the far end of the Institute, causing wastes to be taken across the Institute, can pose a danger to the community. A study has shown that the cancer risk doubled for

children living within 5 kilometers of an incinerator (Moench, 2013). For IRDP, it is within 200 meters, not close to the dispensary where medical waste is generated and only to be carried across the Campus.

The solid waste-dumping pit has no system to separate wastes; separation is done at the site by scavengers who come to look for recyclable materials, which they sell in town. This leads to the spreading of wastes around the area (See Plate 5), a situation worsened by animals such as dogs and cats from the nearby community, as Kimani et al. (n.d) noted in a study on environmental pollution and impacts on public health. Sometimes, minor explosions occur from burning pressurized cans and bottles. Familiar sources of pressurized cans and bottles are perfume and mosquito cans. Waste burning at the dumping pit and cooking using the unimproved charcoal stove as seen in Plate 1 and 5, and at the incinerator (Plate 6) is against the requirement of a sustainable healthy environment which emphasizes the use of the natural environment by reducing pollution and reducing consumption by re-use and or recycle where possible (Nweke & Sanders, 2009; Drexhage & Murphy, 2010; Moench, 2013). Unimproved cooking stoves use more charcoal, leading to more deforestation and land degradation through soil erosion and lack of soil fertility (Moreno, n.d). Deforestation activity causes anthropogenic air pollution (Scienceclarified, n.d). More deforestation means a reduction of windbreakers; the more the wind, the dustier the place, and hence air pollution. Cooking using fuelwood is the primary source of indoor air pollution, which affects the health of many people (Bradford, 2015; Briggs, 2016), and maybe the primary cause of acute respiratory infection to IRDP members as reported at the dispensary. According to the WHO (2014: 2), air pollution kills more people than earlier thought.

After analyzing the risk factors and considering revisions in methodology, WHO estimates indoor air pollution was linked to 4.3 million deaths in 2012 in households cooking over coal, wood, and biomass stoves. The new estimate is explained by better information about pollution exposures among the estimated 2.9 billion people living in homes using wood, coal, or dung as their primary cooking fuel (WHO, 2014: 2).

The use of fuelwood also contributes to greenhouse gasses (Nweke & Sanders, 2009; Conniff, 2016). Land degradation as a result of deforestation for fuelwood production also affects farming activities by causing difficulty for rural people to produce enough to meet their daily needs and have a surplus for sale to get income to meet other

social services needs, including paying for environmentally friendly energy. This, in turn, affects people's quality of life in rural areas.

Another problem noted at IRDP was repeatedly overflowing wastewater from toilets and septic tanks. This problem was associated with the system's poor design, overcrowding of users, broken water tapes, and blocking of the pipes. The overflowing fecal situation causes stress among IRDP members; it is an eye-sore. It was noted that users of the toileting facilities who lack knowledge on how to dispose of sanitary pads caused frequently blocking (Kaseva & Mbuligwe, 2007; Sommer, 2010; Jewitt & Ryley, 2014). This is a development issue, which came without proper preparation among many users. Unfortunately, menstruation issues among women, especially young girls in Tanzania, are considered taboo to talk about (Kanyemba, 2011; House et al., 2012; Guya et al., 2014). On the other hand, the increased rate of blockage is costly to the Institute; the money that could be used for some other development purpose like landscaping, improving teaching, and researching facilitation to enhance the quality of life within and outside the IRDP boundaries is used to service the unplanned sanitation system.

Students apply pesticides to kill pests like cockroaches and mosquitoes in other cases. Pesticides are another source of indoor air pollution, and they contain chemicals that are dangerous to human health (Kishimba et al., 2004). Unfortunately, fumigations that occur three times a year in every four months' interval were not recorded as the source of air pollution and more severe indoor air pollution. Also, repainting that is done every after four to five years as well cause air pollution to the environment (Kishimba et al., 2004). In many cases, some of the pesticides, paints, and chemicals used for fumigation have no label to show the ingredients that could help in environmental health assessment. Most of them have Tanzania's Bureau of Standard (TBS) label, which they use to legalize the use.

5.0 IRDP environmental health vision

The visioning exercise came up with a long wish list for the future of IRDP. Similar items in the list were combined to form the most critical environmental problems in impact categories. Degradation of air quality was taken as the core problem, whose solution would cover a wide range of other issues and would significantly impact human health, ecology, and the quality of life. Together with the mission, a vision is proposed so that there is sustainable environmental health at IRDP.

The proposed environmental health vision of IRDP is a Tanzania free from environmental health hazards. The mission is based on the original mandate of IRDP, based on the three pillars of training, research, and consultancy:

IRDP, an institution that goes beyond the walls to embrace the nearby and far away communities through its alumni and collaborators, is committed to educating, conducting research, and performing consultancy work with principles that respect environmental health. It promotes the use of electronic means of communication to reduce the use of paper; it promotes the regular planting of trees; it promotes the processes of recycling and use of recycled resources; it encourages the use of compost manure as fertilizer for its plants on Campus.

With this vision and mission, the hope is that the environmental health of IRDP and beyond is defined, understood, and acted upon to protect it, on the one hand, and to improve where there are health hazards, on the other hand. Other institutions are encouraged to learn from this experience.

6.0 Concluding remarks

The contribution of environmental health assessment in improving the quality of life of the people in any community must be given an upper hand. We take for granted issues related to the health of the environment where we live. We finally realize that causative agents of an unhealthy environment surround us, and we are the perpetrators of it. We need to institute simple mechanisms in our daily living and working spaces that can now and then send us to thinking about how we impact the health of the environment and what steps we need to take to regulate our actions to mitigate damages done. On this note, it is suggested that an environmental health committee is put in place, with representatives from all the departments. The committee can have an annual environmental health assessment report; however, monthly environmental health observations can be very healthy to keep the Institute on the healthy path.

More specifically, the training institutions with their expertise advantage and the possibility of creating spread effects to reach a large population through their students may be a starting point. Let the training institutions practice their teaching: let them walk the talk.

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